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**THE ROLE OF INNOVATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW
UZBEKISTAN**

Abstract. *The issues are discussed regarding the importance and role in the development of factor innovations economies, especially small businesses, foreign countries, transfer and commercialization of innovation, human capital development and effective to fund the innovation. Presented: a comparative analysis of trends in the development innovation, boost economic growth in developed countries, developing countries and Uzbekistan, as well as its outlook for the medium and long term: clusters and innovative development model.*

Keywords: *Innovation, capital, innovation process, factors of production, innovative entrepreneurship.*

YANGI O‘ZBEKISTON RIVOJLANISHIDA INNOVATSIYALARNING O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada innovatsiyalar iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning eng xarakterli xususiyatlaridan biriga aylanib borayotganligi va bozor rivojlanishini tezlashtiruvchi omil sifatida tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsiyalardan keng foydalanish orqali- tadbirkorlikni jadal rivojlantirishga erishish mumkinligi haqida taklif va tavsiyalar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Innovatsiya, kapital, innovatsion jarayon, ishlab chiqarish omillari, innovatsion strategiya, innovatsion tadbirkorlik.*

РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация. *В данной статье инновации становятся одной из наиболее характерных черт экономического развития и анализируются как фактор, ускоряющий развитие рынка. Также есть предложения и рекомендации, как добиться быстрого развития предпринимательства в современном мире за счет широкого использования инноваций.*

Ключевые слова: *Инновация, капитал, инновационный процесс, факторы производства, инновационное предпринимательство.*

Introduction

Currently, innovation is becoming one of the most characteristic features of economic development. Not long ago, this name reminded of something exotic, unknown and not very clear even among professionals, but now the innovation itself and its concepts are rapidly conquering the world [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]. The international capital market, which plays a significant role in the innovation process and turns innovation into a strategic resource for enterprises, is expanding, and new financial structures are helping it in this regard. The experience of developed countries shows that innovation is often hindered by people's direct negative attitudes and attitudes. However, a paradoxical situation is developing in Uzbekistan that is, the whole society is involved in innovative processes expressing positive attitude and support. In particular, it is reflected in many normative legal documents adopted in Uzbekistan and draft laws widely discussed in social networks. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 27, 2020 on innovative activity, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Scientific Activity", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 22, 2018 "On the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 Presidential Decree on the State Program for the Implementation of the Strategy of Actions in the Five Priority Areas of Development in the Year of Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies", by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5975 dated March 26, 2020, "On measures to fundamentally update the state policy on economic development and

poverty reduction", "On the activities of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its system organizations on organization" No. PQ-4653 dated March 26, 2020, "Improving the system of attracting the population to entrepreneurship and developing entrepreneurship on additional measures" Resolution No. PQ-4862 of October 13, 2020, "On effective organization of the activities of the entrepreneurship development agency under the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan Among them are normative documents such as the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 17, 2021. The purpose of adopting these documents is to develop business activities, to create favorable conditions for the creation and development of new entrepreneurs, to help increase the potential and efficiency of the innovative system, and to create a regulatory, financial and informational environment favorable for innovation. It is also to increase competitiveness and productivity in the industry, to encourage the increase of the share of high-tech products, to increase production and to increase the share in the structure of production and export, to expand the use of innovative technologies and advanced management.

Research methodology

The aim of the research work is to help increase the potential and efficiency of the system through the innovative development of the economy and the creation of new entrepreneurs. The tasks of the research are researching the stages of increasing competitiveness and productivity in the industry and justifying its specific features; to stimulate the increase of the share of high-tech products, to increase the production and increase the share in the structure of production and export, to identify the factors affecting the expansion of the use of innovative technologies and advanced management.

Analysis of literature on the topic

According to some authors, there is both a traditional economy and a new economy that is developing on a different basis. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the positive aspects of both of these models without opposing them, because it shows that a new one is gradually developing at the core of the traditional economy. Indeed, it is true that innovation has become a factor of production in the modern world. It is known that traditionally there are three factors of production: land, labor and capital. They were first analyzed by JB Sey. [5,6] Currently, these factors usually include the ability of entrepreneurs and, according to some authors, the information factor, thus emphasizing the role of information in economic development. In our opinion, it would be more correct to replace entrepreneurial opportunities with innovation or to connect both new factors with traditional factors. Currently, by studying the factors of production, the analysis is carried out more deeply and each factor is broken down. Land or natural factors are factors that do not provide long-term competitive advantages when used as the basis of entrepreneurship. In addition, many types of natural resources are non-renewable and can be exhausted after some time. On the other hand, the innovative factor is practically inexhaustible and it creates innovations that can be introduced into production; their expansion can ensure long-term competitiveness, because it is currently based on new,

especially developed factors. In fact, such a point of view cannot be called "absolutely new". Analyzing the factors of production mentioned above, "Sey" emphasizes the role of the entrepreneur, because he coordinates the following factors of production: land, capital and labor, as well as the labor factor, which he used very widely, including not only labor, but also took into account scientific conclusions and knowledge necessary for product production and organization of production. English scientist GA Hobson expressed this idea more vividly and included creative abilities in the factors of production. [10,11,12,13,14] Analyzing the part of the economic system where new products appear, new markets appear, and new technologies are introduced, he called it "progressive production field" he called. Now we call it the innovation economy. Of course, in the course of studying such a phenomenon as innovation, one should not forget the names of two scientists, that is, N. Kondratiev and the Austrian JAS Schumpeter. It was Schumpeter who first defined the concept of innovation in his study "Theory of Economic Development". [15,16,17,18,19] He interpreted innovation as a scientific and organizational combination of existing production factors aimed at solving commercial problems. Schumpeter directly noticed the source of development of economic systems in innovations. Because specific content innovation is change, they point out five typical changes:

1. Provision of new technologies, new technological processes or new production markets;
2. Introduction of products with new features;
3. Use of new raw materials;
4. Changes in production organization and material and technical support of production;
5. Emergence of new markets.

In addition, he used the concept of innovation and explained it as changes, the purpose of which is to introduce and use new types of consumer goods, new production and means of transport in the form of new production organization. When describing innovation, Schumpeter always emphasized the role of the entrepreneur in this process, because it is the entrepreneur who is the driving force, implements new inventions and receives the profit as a reward. Not all inventions become innovations. Innovations are inventions that bring profit and satisfy market demand. In other words, thanks to science, an idea that can be implemented appears, and the next step is the commercialization of this idea, which turns the invention into an innovation, which brings income. It says: If science is the process of converting money into knowledge, "Economics and Innovative Technologies", innovation is the process of converting knowledge into money with added value. Kondratiev justified the idea that economic cycles (waves) have different lengths: long - 48-55 years, medium - 7-11 years and short - 3-3.5 years. His most important contribution is related to the study of long waves. To support his theory, he analyzed a large amount of factual material covering the four most developed countries - Great Britain, France, Germany and the United States. The studies conducted were related to the dynamics of prices, interest rates, wages, foreign trade volume and the dynamics of basic industrial goods. The time period under analysis was extended to 140 years. Research has confirmed the existence of long waves and science, its discoveries, the

uneven development of science and technology, innovations, etc. have been noted as one of the reasons (Kondratiev N. (1925)). [18,19,22] Kondratiev discovered empirical patterns associated with long waves. Before the development of the wave and at its beginning, deep changes occur in the economic life of society associated with important changes in technology (important technological discoveries and inventions took place). He considered scientific and technical innovations to be the main factor. Innovation creates excitement by changing the economic environment from its trend to an upward trend. Kondratiev also showed that innovations are unevenly distributed over time. They appear in groups or, in modern language, clusters. Therefore, in the study of Kondratiev, we can find one of the first examples of the use of the cluster approach. Currently, Kondratiev's recommendations can be used in the development of innovative strategies. [20,21,22,23,24,25] The role of technological cycles is manifested in the development of the economy and society, which, on the one hand, increases the mass of capital production, and also increases its technological level. On the other hand, the skill level of the workforce and management will increase due to improved education and skills. Over time, with the achievement of a high technological level of production, the innovative characteristics of the labor force are the characteristics that grow the fastest, because the skilled labor force not only absorbs new technologies faster and uses them more efficiently, but also creates these technologies in production. Schumpeter JA in his "Business Cycles" (1939) combined N. Kondratiev's long wave theory with his innovation theory, resulting in the first cyclical theory of development.[12,.20,21] According to him, the cyclical development of the economy is mainly related to the internal mechanism of the system, and it is an innovative process. Research methodology The article uses methods of scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction. The data of this research is taken from official sources and the economy of well-known economists in development of innovation The study of innovative entrepreneurship was achieved based on the comparative analysis of scientific and theoretical views on the role of b, summarizing foreign experiences and the results obtained in our country.

Analysis and results

If we compare the innovative processes in our country with the situation in developed countries, now the developed countries of the world have been under the influence of the innovative economy and the fifth technological cycle (long wave) for more than 15 years. What should countries do that are only able to enter the fifth wave, and even beyond? " Will they reach these countries first of all, starting their scientific research in new high-tech directions? Apparently, this is very problematic. However, this prevents these countries, especially in our country, from using the technologies created by other countries and using them in the development of their economy, trying to surpass developed countries by creating as many conditions as possible for foreign investments to enter the country. does not Some time ago, this experiment was carried out in Japan, South Korea and other countries. In fact, the opportunities provided by innovation and the positive aspects of globalization were first of all captured by South-East Asian countries (often called "tigers"), such as South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore,

as well as the Celts. The "tiger" is Ireland, one of the leaders in the field of innovation. These countries can serve as a paradigm for Uzbekistan, because our country, with its small market, poor traditional resources, can only develop successfully if it chooses an innovative path using its competitive unique non-traditional resources. The competitiveness of the country develops on the basis of the competitiveness of individual enterprises. Every business uses its own strategy to achieve competitive advantage. However, the evolution and development of successful companies will be similar in nature as companies create competitive advantages based on innovation. The reason for the weakness of innovative processes in the enterprises of our country is due to the influence of the following factors:

- low number of scientists working in industry, as well as low percentage of scientists and researchers in the labor force;
- not to enter the field of high technology patenting;
- weak cooperation between the production sector and universities;
- relative failure of innovation promotion and activity of entrepreneurship support mechanisms;
- complex procedures for starting a business; insufficient quality of technological education.

It is also worth noting the concept of the so-called "European innovation paradox" from the world experience - on the one hand, when assessing the share of investments in education and science in the GDP, as well as the percentage of highly educated people in the population in most countries of the European Union, the USA or even better than Japan. Europe also surpasses them in terms of indicators of scientific potential (for example, the number of Nobel Prize winners, SCI publications, number of scientists with doctoral degrees). Nevertheless, the productivity of the economy in the European Union is twice as low as that of the United States, and its trade balance with the United States is negative. Students from different parts of the world are trying to study in higher educational institutions of the USA. The United States itself is a very successful country in the use of innovation, commercializing knowledge created not only in its own country, but also around the world. The best specialists in the field of higher education and research (project managers, researchers, highly educated technology specialists) move to the USA. Europe is betting on training and higher education at US companies. According to these and similar facts, the term "European innovation paradox" also appeared. From the above, we can conclude that "Economy and innovative technologies" innovation is the main driving force. Thus, innovation provides an opportunity to develop a competitive economy. In recent years, not only economists, but also politicians have understood this. To achieve the main goals, it is necessary to allocate 3% of the gross domestic product to research and development, to increase the employment rate to 70%, to reduce bureaucracy, to eliminate corruption, and to promote entrepreneurship. If these problems are solved, our country's economy will achieve great success in innovative development.

It is envisaged to allocate funds from state budgets for scientific research and innovation and increase the volume of its provision. In particular, three main directions are given priority:

- investment in education and formation and increase of intellectual property;
- strengthening competitiveness in industry and service sector;
- establishment of monocenters in the labor market. It can be seen that in all the cases mentioned above, increasing competitiveness is related to innovation.

Creating a coordinated and common space for research and knowledge extension is a necessity for effective knowledge exchange between countries and individual enterprises. It is not only about supporting research and development of technologies and protection of intellectual property rights, but also about ensuring the spread and diffusion of innovations, because where innovations are introduced, the results are as expected. A new trend in the use of innovations has formed in Uzbekistan's industry. Until then, industries related to the processing of natural resources with the use of cheap labor dominated. However, today Uzbekistan aims for a completely new approach to the use of natural resources. A clear example of this is the new UzGTL plant, which has launched the production of products with high added value based on the deep processing of natural gas. Due to such large projects, Uzbekistan is gradually abandoning the export of raw natural gas and reducing the import of oil products. This indicates that a significant contribution is being made to strengthening our energy independence. This UzGTL complex, which is considered one of the largest investment projects not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the CIS countries, is also an example of innovative production. Also, one of the most modern and innovative in the territory of the CIS is the central control panel of the enterprise and the central factory laboratory. The new enterprise has the capacity to process 3.6 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year and produce 1.5 million tons of finished products - aviation kerosene, diesel fuel, naphtha, liquefied gas - based on the GTL, i.e. "gas-to-liquid" technology. Until now, such a plant has been established in only 4 countries in the world - Qatar, Nigeria, South African Republic and Malaysia. Oil products and hydrocarbon raw materials with a total value of 1 billion US dollars or more than 12.8 trillion soums annually are produced here. Extraction of value-added products from natural gas based on GTL technology is carried out in three stages. Modern types of fuel made on the basis of this technology are environmentally friendly and clean. This, in turn, corresponds to the principle of not harming nature, which has become an urgent issue today. Take GTL diesel fuel for example. GTL diesel with a high technical specification and almost no sulfur content does not emit significant emissions into the atmosphere. Also, GTL kerosene offers airlines a safe and cost-effective way to reduce emissions. At the same time, electricity is generated autonomously due to the excess steam generated during the production process. That is, the issue of supplying the "Uzbekistan GTL" plant with electricity was also solved in an innovative way. Thus, the enterprise not only independently produces the electricity necessary for its activities, but also supplies the additional amount of electricity produced to the national power grids in necessary cases. In addition, modern high-quality UzGTL products

from processed gas based on innovative technologies work is issued. At the same time, the naphtha produced at the UzGTL plant will be sent for processing to the production capacity expansion facilities of the "Shortan Gas Chemical Complex" to increase the production of polymer products, thereby creating a single oil-gas-chemical cluster. It should be noted that in the creation of the UzGTL synthetic liquid fuel production project, advanced technological solutions of leading companies such as Sasol (South Africa), Haldor Topsøe (Denmark), Chevron (USA) and Honeywell were used. UzGTL products meeting high international standards are delivered primarily to cover the republic's domestic need for petroleum products, in particular, diesel fuel and kerosene, as well as liquefied gas. In addition, since the manufactured products are of high quality, there will be an opportunity to export. It should be noted that the UzGTL plant is an example of structural changes in the deep processing of hydrocarbon raw materials in Uzbekistan and is an indicator of the rate of development of the petrochemical industry of our country.

Conclusions and suggestions.

In conclusion, in modern enterprises engaged in innovative entrepreneurship and using foreign experience in the production process and introducing innovations, wages are 2-3 times higher than traditional enterprises, productivity is 2 double increase, especially the quality and well-being of workers' living standards compared to before, shows the positive aspects of today's innovative economic reforms. But along with the progress being made, there are also problems to be solved.

In particular:

- that our entrepreneurs do not have sufficient skills in business management;
- worker inability of x people to absorb news quickly;
- they cannot adequately assess internal and external risks, the need for innovation, and their position in the world market;
- not enough attention is paid to the development of enterprises, increase of competitiveness;
- There are also many problems in the organization of the business environment and the development of the innovation promotion structure. We consider the following suggestions and recommendations appropriate for solving these problems:
 - it is necessary to increase the role of private business in the process of funding scientific research, which will give an impetus to increase the effectiveness of investments in research and development;
 - it is necessary to increase the level of investments necessary for innovation and strengthen competition;
 - It is necessary to support the marketing search system for developments, which is the main element of stimulating innovation and foreign patenting of scientific developments created in Uzbekistan.

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Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

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Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

Til(lar)i: o'zbek, rus, ingliz

Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

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